

Experimental Proof of the Energy Advantage of In-Network Intelligence

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Abstract—According to the current architectural visions, 6G is expected to host various new demanding use cases like massive twinning, massive robots and cobots, and the Tactile Internet. This complex scenario will pose unprecedented challenges to network management and orchestration, which have required the employment of massive in-network intelligence. In-network intelligence will help 6G to achieve its performance indicators in terms of latency and resilience via prediction and proactive management. However, this will imply the significant increase of energy usage for intelligent operations like data mining and classification, learning, and decision-making. This is in contrast with the 6G objectives of sustainability and significant energy cost reduction. Then, the evaluation of the trade-off between in-network intelligence performance and energy usage has a key role. In this context, a testbed has been constructed to measure the energy cost of in-network intelligence systems, where the power cost of an emulated network system, deployed on the stand-alone host hardware, is measured in real-time. Using a vertical in-network intelligence application, our experiments have shown that the in-network intelligence system uses less power than a traditional centralized system, in turn contributing to higher energy efficiency. With increased in-network intelligence resources, less power is consumed, reaching a maximum reduction of 20% in our experiments. Additionally, the results show that power savings of in-network intelligence also come from its reduced service time. This article illustrates the advantages of in-network computing to help reducing the energy usage of in-network intelligence while also achieving the 6G performance

indicators.

Index Terms—testbed, green communication, in-network computing, blind source separation, network softwarization

I. INTRODUCTION

The standardization of 5G networks is reaching its end, and since a couple of years, the research and industrial communities have started the study and research of future 6G communication networks. In this sense, various governments have started their flagship 6G projects to provide the design guidelines for the the future generation networks. In the EU, the Hexa-X project [1] represents the flagship for 6G. 6G vision aims at connecting three different worlds and to manage their interactions: a human world of senses, intelligence, and values, with a digital world of information, communication and computing, together with a physical world of objects and organisms. In this sense, trustworthiness, digital inclusiveness, resilience, and sustainability become the conceptual backbone of the architectural design. Regarding sustainability, it is also fundamental that the network development significantly target energy efficiency, towards minimum CO₂ footprint.

In order for 6G to ensure the above promises and become the pillar of the society (providing connectivity and computing resources to all the aspects of human life), an architectural evolution is necessary. In fact, even if 5G has pushed the network performances quite ahead, the technological achievement is not enough to guarantee the necessary requirements to various services like massive robot control, human-machine interaction and co-working, and massive telepresence. In this context, some initial works have been published to provide architectural design guidelines for 6G, like [2].

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First, 6G architecture will complete the initial network softwarization process that has been started with 5G. The network infrastructure will host an end-to-end softwarized network continuum, which will dynamically place abstracted network resources, functionalities, protocols, operations, etc. This network continuum will be orchestrated by a combination of centralised and distributed intelligence, which will not be merely a service running on the network but it will become an inherent element of the network itself. This will be fundamental to achieve the very low end-to-end latency and resilience that the new use cases are going to need. In-network intelligence will focus not only on active orchestration and management but also on proactive ones. The proactivity becomes necessary to anticipate network states and so reducing the latency beyond its physical possibilities. In this sense, the price to pay is terms of reliability of decision-making (network management becomes statistical) and in terms of energy cost. In fact, massive employment of intelligence in the network can highly increase the energy cost of control traffic and computing for data mining and classification, for learning, decision-making, and acting on the infrastructure. That is why, it becomes pivotal to mitigate and minimise the trade-off between in-network intelligence cost and energy usage. This article tackles this issue, by providing the experimental proof of an in-network intelligence solution, which is capable of ensuring high energy efficiency, while maintaining or reducing the end-to-end latency.

Existing studies on in-network intelligence have focused primarily on how to integrate computational tasks into the network to accelerate data processing across the Internet of Things (IoT). For instance, the work in [3] decomposes an image detection job into a chain of service functions. It reduces latency by more than 25% as processing can simply be done at a closer node. Similarly, in [4], a real-time wire-following service for computer vision, is decomposed and deployed in a network with a series of programmable network devices. [5] progressively performs the centralized audio processing tasks in the network, resulting in a 30% reduction in task latency. These works meet the low latency requirement by embedding computational tasks into the network. However, the network also has to perform data processing tasks besides data transmission. The data processing tasks introduced certainly affect the energy consumption of the whole network.

This paper presents a realistic testbed for measuring the energy performance of an in-network intelligence system. In this testbed, a simulated in-network intelligence system is hosted on a stand-alone hardware, and an external circuit measures the voltage and DC current variations of a Raspberry Pi. These variations are converted to power by an external analysis unit, which is synchronized with the simulated in-network intelligence system. This paper uses a widely used acoustic pre-processing application "blind source separation", as the measurement object. Through quantitative analysis using a practical dataset, it is found that the in-network intelligence method progressive ICA (pICA) reduces the energy consumption by up to 20% compared to the traditional centralized

Fig. 1: The schematic architecture of the in-network Blind Source Separation system [5].

method Centralized ICA (cICA). Moreover, this reduction becomes more significant as the number of network devices participating in the computation increases. The findings of this paper suggest that in-network intelligence not only satisfies the need for low latency, but also has significant advantages in terms of energy consumption.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. First, we provide the system setup and related works on the measurement object Blind Source Separation (BSS) in Section II. Following that, Section III introduces the design of the testbed. Section IV covers the experiment setup and discussions about the measurement results.

II. BACKGROUND

An in-network intelligence system, pICA [5], is presented in this section to address a vertical application of BSS. It will serve as an object of observation in our testbed during future experiments.

A. System Setup

The scenario considered here is illustrated in Fig. 1. Specifically, each IoT sensor collects sound data from the machine "source" to which it is connected. An audio sound signal interferes with the sound of other machines in the air (as noise). Each IoT sensor continuously sends the collected data to a client node. The client node can be a WiFi Access Point (AP) or a cellular base station of a (non-public) network. This client node continuously forwards data from all sensors to the back-end "Server" node via a forwarding path. This path can be dynamically determined based on a routing protocol or statically configured. The forwarding path includes several intermediate "nodes i " and "nodes $i+1$ ", for a total number of k nodes. In a Software Defined Networking (SDN), the intermediate nodes are SDN switches, which also own computing resources to host Network Function Virtualization (NFV).

Consider this system with n working machines, indexed by i . The i^{th} work machine generates the raw data denoted by s_i . As mentioned before, the original signal data s_i will be distorted into mixed data x_i due to mutual interference. With m time slots, the data collected at the client node is represented by data matrix X . Thus, the original separated X is the source matrix S . This process of source signal mixing is expressed as BSS, which is denoted as follows:

$$X = A \times S, \quad (1)$$

where the mixing of the source data S into X is represented by the mixing matrix A . Mathematically, a BSS problem is the inverse of Eq. (1):

$$\hat{S} = A^{-1} \times X = W \times X, \quad (2)$$

where the recovered data \hat{S} is estimated by deriving the separation matrix W , which will be applied to the input data X for data separation.

B. Related Work

When it comes to a BSS problem, many centralized machine learning-based solutions are available. One type is Neural Network (NN)-based Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions such as Y-Net [6] and Conv-TasNet [7]. However, NN-based solutions are less interesting for in-network computing concepts, because (i) it is difficult to obtain sufficient representative and labeled training data; (ii) training an NN model is time and resource-consuming, and (iii) once deployed on a network node, the NN model cannot be updated flexibly. Moreover, NN-based solutions require special hardware (e.g., GPUs) to maximize their performance, which is not very likely to be present on network devices. Another type of algorithms is the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) based on computational intelligence. ICA algorithms work directly with the input data and require only general hardware capabilities. Typical ICA algorithms are FastICA [8], InfoMax [9], and CdICA [10]. ICA-based solutions do not constrain them; thus, they are more feasible for in-network intelligence solutions.

However, these cICA algorithms cannot be straightforwardly implemented to an in-network intelligence concept. The main reason is that they require all the data to compute the final result, while the data in the network are forwarded sequentially by the network nodes in the forwarding path in the form of packets [11]. Therefore, simply executing the ICA algorithm on each node is equivalent to repeating the same procedure on multiple nodes. Unfortunately, this does not improve the performance of latency.

In this sense, [5], [12]–[14] have realized this problem and proposed distributed variants of ICA for in-network intelligence. Adaptive Extraction-Based Independent Component Analysis (AeICA) proposed in [12] has the potential to be performed in the network but it can be sensitive to the initial parameter configuration, which depends heavily on the a priori knowledge of the input data. NJICA, proposed in [13], utilizes a generic computing architecture of commodity servers to distribute the operation of ICA. However, NJICA only considers transforming centralized ICA algorithms into distributed versions and ignores the forwarding layer problem. Its drawback is the processing delay since the data stream is delayed by caching and computation operations in several intermediate network nodes. The work in [5] extended both the application and forwarding layers in the network stack by proposing pICA. pICA contains a progressive computational logic and a computational state-based network packet forwarding mechanism to realize in-network intelligence, which accelerates the whole BSS service.

Current state-of-the-art methods have shown that in-network intelligence approaches offer huge advantages in terms of latency. However, in-network intelligence requires the network to further integrate computational tasks in addition to data forwarding tasks. Since energy usage is becoming more and more

Fig. 2: The structure of the testbed.

critical, the concern of whether the additional computational tasks of in-network intelligence will further increase the energy cost is a major concern, we deal with in this paper. Therefore, we built a testbed to measure and analyze the performance of the in-network intelligence approach in terms of power and subsequently energy cost.

III. TESTBED

This section first presents the design principle of the testbed. Following this, the structure of the testbed is described in detail. At the end, the method for processing the measurement data is given.

A. Design Principle

The testbed consists of three units: network unit, measurement unit, and analysis unit, as shown in Fig. 2. The design principle of the testbed is as follows.

First, the network unit is in charge of hosting network services. A stand-alone host hardware is used in the network unit to host the entire network, whose energy consumption is expected to be measured. The network service of the in-network computing application is deployed in this network. Additionally, a power supply in the network unit supplies the host hardware.

Second, the energy cost of the network unit is measured by the measurement unit. A power monitoring sensor device is needed in this unit. The power is obtained by measuring the voltage and current variations of the host hardware with a pre-defined sampling rate.

Third, the analysis unit is responsible for recording the measured voltage and current from the measurement unit. By synchronizing the service time of the network service in the network unit, the power of the network service during the duration of the service time can be obtained. Based on the service time and power, the overall energy cost of the network service can be obtained.

The next section will describe the device selection and setup of the testbed’s three units in detail.

B. Structure of Testbed

1) *Network Unit*: The main task of the network unit is to host network services. We chose the Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ as the stand-alone hardware in the “network unit”. The main reasons for this are as follows: (i) The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ has no energy optimization features compared to

Fig. 3: The architecture of the network unit.

compact hosts such as Personal Computers (PCs) and laptops. This ensures that when testing the energy usage of different network services on the testbed, the basic energy consumed by the host hardware is not altered so as to avoid the impact of the deviation of the energy used by the host hardware; (ii) The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ consumes less energy than a large server. This avoids the large energy consumption of the host hardware itself to cover the small variations in energy consumption of the network services to be tested, thus improving the measurement accuracy of the whole testbed; (iii) The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+ supports generic Linux Operating Systems (OSs) and is equipped with communication and processing modules. This enhances the ease of deploying network services on it.

In this testbed, the Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+, as the host hardware, is equipped with Linux Ubuntu 18.04 as the host OS. A network emulator, Communication Networks Emulator (ComNetsEmu) [15], is used to build the SDN network. This SDN network can perform data forwarding tasks and is capable of integrating in-network computational logic. The computing logic is containerized as NFV and attached to the SDN switches. The architecture of “network unit” is illustrated in Fig. 3. Such architecture ensures that the host hardware can emulate the entire network and the flexibility to deploy different in-network intelligence services.

2) *Measurement Unit*: For the measurement unit, we chose the Adafruit INA219 sensor device for power monitoring. Adafruit INA219B can measure high side voltage $V(t)$ and DC current $I(t)$ at time instant t with 1% accuracy.

Since the host hardware is powered through a USB cable, Adafruit INA219 measures the voltage and current on it. The USB cable between the power supply and the host hardware is cut into two parts. At the cutting point, the power supply inflow end (near the power supply) is connected to “VIN+” of the Adafruit INA219B, and the power supply outflow end (near the host hardware) is connected to “VIN-” of the Adafruit INA219B. In this way, real-time voltage and current changes of the host hardware can be measured and the measurement frequency of the Adafruit INA219B can be adjusted.

3) *Analysis Unit*: In the analysis unit, the Arduino UNO R3 is responsible for recording the real-time voltage and current obtained by the measurement unit. At the same time, Arduino UNO R3 is also responsible for supplying power to the power monitoring sensor device in the measurement unit. As shown in Fig. 2, there are three wires connecting between the Adafruit INA219 and the Arduino UNO R3, which are responsible for voltage reading, current reading, and power

supply, respectively. Note that, the power supply at this point does not affect the network unit because they are completely independent and do not interact with each other.

The analysis unit also contains a PC responsible for analyzing the measured data. The PC can obtain real-time voltage $V(t)$ and DC current $I(t)$ measurements from the Arduino UNO R3 and assign timestamps to these measurements. At the same time, the PC synchronizes timing with the host hardware (Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+) in the network unit and obtains the service time T of the network service. Once the network service is completed, the PC can retrieve the corresponding voltage and current measurements during the service time and hence determine the energy consumption of the network service.

C. Measurement

After obtaining the real-time voltage $V(t)$ and DC current $I(t)$ from the analysis unit, the power at time instant t can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$P(t) = V(t) \times I(t), \quad (3)$$

where $P(t)$ is the power of the whole emulated network at time instant t .

Since the power of the network service is a continuous value and this power varies over the service time T , however, the measured value is discrete. Therefore, the analysis unit calculates the total energy cost by integrating the power over the service time as follows:

$$E = P(t) \times T = \int_0^T P(t) dt. \quad (4)$$

By doing so, it has the advantage that the energy value calculated based on the power and the service time is as close as possible to the realistic continuous energy consumption.

IV. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

This section will introduce the experiment setting, followed by numerical evaluations and discussions of the energy and power consumption measured by the testbed.

A. Experiment Setting

1) *Dataset*: The evaluation in this paper employed the realistic dataset of Sound Dataset for Malfunctioning Industrial Machine Investigation and Inspection (MIMII) [16]. MIMII is an acoustic dataset widely used for faulty industrial machine detection and contains 26092 acoustic segments of normal and abnormal operation from four types of real machines: valves, pumps, fans, and slides. Each segment is single-channel, 10 seconds in length, and has a sampling rate of 16,000 Hz. We randomly selected all $n = 4$ types of sound sources from the dataset to construct the sound source signal S and mixed them with standard normal distribution to simulate mixing cases (refer to Eq. (1)). In this way, various source data types and mixing scenarios are covered.

2) *Setup*: In this paper, the network topology of the testbed is linear, with client and server connected by k SDN switches at both ends (see Fig. 1). The network scale gradually increases from $k = 0$ to $k = 5$ SDN switches, representing the growing computational resources of in-network intelligence, in total six network settings.

pICA [5], designed based on in-network intelligence, is the evaluated system. Its computational logic is deployed as NFVs on the SDN switches in the testbed. With pICA, the SDN switches perform computation and transmission tasks at the same time.

Besides, cICA without in-network intelligence capability is employed as a reference system, the most widely used centralized BSS method [17]. cICA's computational logic is deployed centralized on the server, while only transmission task is performed on the SDN switches. Both systems use identical hardware and system parameters. It is worth noting that when $k = 0$, pICA is equivalent to cICA because there are no computational resources available in the network for in-network computing. The experiments were all conducted on the testbed proposed in Section III-B. Both pICA and cICA were implemented in Python.

3) *Metrics*: In this paper, the following three metrics are used to evaluate the energy consumption of in-network intelligence methods.

- Energy cost ratio of pICA and cICA r_E :

$$r_E = \frac{E_{pICA}}{E_{cICA}} \times 100, \quad (5)$$

where E_{pICA} and E_{cICA} are the energy cost of pICA and cICA, obtained following Eq. (4). r_E indicates the global energy consumption of the system. Specifically, pICA and cICA perform the same task, and the energy consumption ratio of in-network intelligence capable pICA to the reference cICA is compared. The smaller the ratio, the more energy-efficient the cICA is. For r greater than 100%, pICA consumes more energy than cICA for the same task.

- Service time ratio of pICA and cICA r_T :

$$r_T = \frac{T_{pICA}}{T_{cICA}}, \quad (6)$$

where T_{pICA} and T_{cICA} are the end-to-end service time of pICA and cICA. The service time covers all the time from the first packet sent by the client to the server getting the final separated data, including the computation time and transmission time. In this paper, we measured service time using the Python module `time` with a precision of 0.1 ms. r_T represents the ratio of pICA service time compared to cICA service time. A smaller r_T means that the service time of pICA is shorter than that of cICA.

- Power cost ratio of pICA and cICA r_P :

$$r_P = \frac{P_{pICA}}{P_{cICA}}, \quad (7)$$

where P_{pICA} and P_{cICA} are the mean power cost of pICA and cICA over their service time T_{pICA} and T_{cICA} .

Fig. 4: The energy cost of Blind Source Separation with and without in-network intelligence.

r_P shows the unit time energy consumption ratio of pICA compared to cICA. An r_P greater than 1 means that pICA consumes more energy per unit time than cICA, and vice versa, pICA consumes less energy per unit time.

For each given number of SDN switch k , we run our experiment 50 times to eliminate the randomness of the measurement statistics. The measurement unit of the testbed performed power measurements at a frequency of 5 Hz.

B. Energy Cost

Fig. 4 provides the energy cost ratio r_E of the selected system pICA and cICA. It can be observed that pICA gains energy consumption saving with the network setting from $k = 2$ SDN switches and more saving with the increasing number of the SDN switches k . The gap becomes maximum when k increases to 5. Numerically, the median energy consumption of pICA decreases from 100% to ca. 80%, which is a 20% reduction. This shows that pICA is more energy-efficient when there are enough network resources compared with cICA, and this energy-saving becomes more significant as the network resources increase.

Additionally, when $k = 0$, the two systems show similar energy consumption because there is no computing in the network with the SDN switch. Because in the case of $k = 0$, pICA and cICA are equivalent. When $k = 1$, pICA consumes ca. 2% more energy than cICA slightly. This may be due to the fact that the additional energy consumption of the network for scheduling computation and transmission tasks is greater than the energy saved by pICA for blind source separation.

It is noticed that the energy consumption is related to the service time and power, as shown in Eq. (4). It has been shown in [5] that the service time of pICA is shorter than that of cICA, and this acceleration becomes greater with the increase of available network resources (i.e., k SDN switches). Therefore, next, on the basis of the above experimental results, we will investigate whether the energy savings of pICA is only due to the reduction in service time or also due to pICA's integration of computation and transmission.

C. Power and Service Time

The power cost ratio r_P and service time ratio r_T of pICA to cICA are presented in Fig. 5. The median r_P is greater than 100% in all six network settings, and it slightly grows from approximately 100% to 100.65% as the number of SDN switches

Fig. 5: The power and time cost of Blind Source Separation with and without in-network intelligence.

k becomes larger. The observation suggests that although in pICA the SDN switches are performing computational tasks in addition to transmission tasks, the introduction of such computation does not significantly increase power cost. This is due to the progressive design of pICA, which ensures the computational tasks on each SDN switch are lightweight.

On the other hand, r_T changes significantly by 21%, with the median value decreasing from approximately 100% to 79%. This reveals that the reduction in the energy consumption ratio of about 20% observed in the previous section is mainly due to the reduction in service time. But, more importantly, this result is obtained without significantly increasing power consumption per unit time.

Considering the impact of power cost ratio and service time ratio on the energy consumption ratio, one can conclude that a lightweight design of an in-network intelligence system can reduce the system's overall energy consumption. This reduction in energy consumption is due to the reduction in service time of in-network intelligence. This reduction becomes more significant with increased network size/available network resources. In summary, in-network intelligence has a great advantage in greening communication networks.

V. CONCLUSION

The experimental study of energy cost of in-network intelligence is a priority in 6G research since it can prevent the achievement of sustainability. It is also important to find schemes that ensure low energy cost while maintaining the low latency high reliability obtained by in-network intelligence.

In this paper, a testbed is constructed to observe and to prove the performance of in-network intelligence systems in terms of energy usage. The power of a simulated network system deployed on stand-alone host hardware is measured in real time, and the network system synchronizes the network service time with the measurement and analysis unit to obtain the total energy consumption of a given network service. By comparing with the traditional centralized system, it is found that the in-network intelligence system has excellent performance in terms of energy consumption. Specifically, as the resources available for the in-network intelligence system increase, the less energy is consumed, reaching a maximum reduction of 20% in the experiments. Moreover, by analyzing power with respect to service time, it is shown that the advantage of in-

network intelligence in terms of energy consumption mainly comes from its reduced service time. The findings of this paper provides an experimental proof of the great improvement that in-network intelligence can provide to energy efficiency. This can be a key design guideline for the realisation of the future 6G network architecture.

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